

OPTIK QURILMALARDAN TIBBIYOTDA FOYDALANISH.

Muxtaram Boboqulova Xamroyevna

Osiyo Xalqaro Universiteti

“Umumtexnik fanlar” kafedrası assisenti
muhtaramboboqulova607@gmail.com

Sattorova Jasmina Sayfullo qizi

Osiyo Xalqaro Universiteti Tibbiyot fakulteti talabasi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10690766>

ANNOSTATSIYA.

Optik qurilmalar tibbiyot sohalarida keng qo'llaniladi. Miopiya yoki gipermetropiya kabi ko'z ko'nikmalarning davriy optik xatoliklari bo'lganda, ko'zoynak yoki ko'z nuqsonlari optik qurilmalar orqali to'g'rilanadi. Tibbiyotda endoskop va mikroskoplar optik qurilmalarni o'z ichiga oladi. Bu vositalar orqali hujjatlarning ichiga kirish va shu hujjatlarni ko'z orqali ko'rish mumkin. Radiologiyada, optik qurilmalar x-nurlar yoki boshqa radiatsiya turini ushlab turadigan optik sistemalarda ishlatiladi. Bu optik qurilmalar orqali rentgen tasvirlarni olish va diagnostika qilish mumkin. Lazerlar tibbiyotda turli jarayonlarda ishlatiladigan optik qurilma turlaridan biridir. Lazer texnika yordamida jigar, ko'z qorni, ko'z bo'yin, angiografiya va boshqa amaliyotlarni o'tkazish mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: lazer texnika,svetoterapiya,optik terapiya,endoskop.

Ba'zi tibbiyot sohalarida, optik qurilmalar terapevtik maqsadlar uchun ishlatiladi. Masalan, svetoterapiya yoki optik terapiya orqali yorug'lik tizimini ta'sir qilib, kishilarning tungi vaqtlarda ko'rish masofasini oshirish uchun foydalaniladi. Optik qurilmalardan tibbiyotda foydalanishning ushbu misollariga qaramasdan, shuningdek, qo'llanilayotgan boshqa ko'plab usullar mavjud. Shunday qilish, optika va qurilma texnologiyasi tibbiyot sohasidagi jarayonlarda yaxshi natijalarga erishish uchun muhimdir. Optik qurilmalar ko'zni o'z ichiga olgan xatoliklarni to'g'rilash uchun ishlatiladi. Bu xatoliklar odatda ko'zning muguz pardasi shikastlanishi tufayli kelib chiqadi va optik qurilmalar, ko'zning optik tizimini o'zgartirib, ob'ektivni to'g'rilyadi. Miopiya holatida, ko'zning ob'ektivi juda kuchli bo'ladi. Optik qurilmalar miopiyani to'g'rilyadi, bu esa ko'z hosil qilgan chiziqlar retinaga to'g'ri yetib kelishishini ta'minlaydi. Gipermetropiya holatida, ko'zning ob'ektivi juda kuchi emas, va chiziqlar retinaga yetib kelmaydi. Optik qurilmalar gipermetropiyani to'g'rilyadi va chiziqlar retinaga to'g'ri yetishishini ta'minlaydi. Optik qurilmalar astigmatizmni to'g'rilyadi va chiziqlar retinaga to'g'ri yetishishini ta'minlaydi. Yosh ulg'aygan sari, ko'z ob'ektivining elastikligi kamayib ketadi, shuning uchun

nazariy ko'z ustiga yaqin masofada joylashgan chiziqlar retinaga yetmaydi. Optik qurilmalar presbiopiyani to'g'rilaydi va yaqin masofada ham, uzoq masofada ham to'g'ri ko'rish imkoniyatini ta'minlaydi. Ko'z sun'iy qurilmalari optik qurilmalar orqali ko'ra olish uchun ham ishlatiladi. Bu sun'iy qurilmalar miopiyani, gipermetropiyani yoki astigmatizmni to'g'rilash uchun moslashtirilgan bo'lib, ko'z optikasini o'zgartiradi. Optik qurilmalar yordamida to'g'rilangan ko'z xatoliklari tibbiyot sohasidagi ko'p xil jarayonlarda qo'llaniladi va insonlarning ko'zni qanday ko'rishini o'zgartirish uchun muhimdir. Agar sizda biron bir ko'z xatoligi bo'lsa yoki ko'zingizda qiyinlikni his qilsangiz, bu holatda eng muhim bo'lgan narsa o'zingizni bir tibbiyot mutaxassisi yoki ko'zlar sohasida mutaxassis bilan konsultatsiya olishdir. Ular sizning xolatingizni tekshirib, moslashtirilgan optik qurilmalar orqali to'g'ri natijalarga erishish uchun kerakli tajribani va bilimni ega bo'ladilar.

ADABIYOTLAR TAHLILI VA METODOLOGIYA

Lazer (Laser Assisted In Situ Keratomileusis) xirurgiya miopiya, gipermetropiya va astigmatizmni davolash uchun juda ommabop bo'lgan optik xirurgiya uslubidir. Bu jarayonda, lazer ko'zning ko'rish qismini to'g'ri tanlash uchun ishlatiladi va ko'zni kuchliroq yoki yumshoqroq qiladi. PRK xirurgiyasi ham ko'zning ko'rishini o'zgartirish maqsadida amalga oshiriladi. Lekin, PRK da ko'zning yuqori qismidagi jild o'chirilib, lazer bilan to'g'rilanadi. PRK jarayonida ta'sir qiladigan zonani tanlash va takomillash davri uzunroq bo'lishi mumkin. Bu optik xirurgiya turi, ko'zga o'rnatilgan sun'iy linzalarni (phakic lens) ishlatish asosida amalga oshiriladi. Bu sun'iy linzalar optik tizimni o'zgartirib, miopiya yoki gipermetropiyani to'g'rilaydi. Bu jarayon, tabiiy ko'z ob'ektivini sun'iy linza bilan almashtirib olishni o'z ichiga oladi. Optik xirurgiyalarni amalga oshirishda, ko'z va optik tizimining holatiga qarab tanlov qilish uchun mutaxassislik va tajriba talab qilinadi. Har bir optik xirurgiya turining o'z bevosita va mahsuloti bor, shuning uchun optik xirurgiyaga yondashgan klinikaga va mutaxassisga muayyanlik bilan murojaat qilish kerak. Optik xirurgiya, ko'zingizdagi xatolikni bartaraf etish uchun samarali va qulay bir usul bo'lib, yana ham keng doirada rivojlanmoqda. Optik qurilmalar, ko'zingizdagi xatoliklarni to'g'rilash uchun olib boriladigan jarayonlardir va salomatlik uchun muhimdir. Ko'zni to'g'ri ko'rish, umumiy salomatlik va hayot sifatini oshirish uchun optik qurilmalardan foydalanish quyidagi muhim sifatlarga ega bo'ladi: oftalmolog, ko'zingizning holatini tekshirib, eng mos optik qurilmani tavsiya etishi mumkin. Optik qurilmalar, ko'zingizni to'g'ri ko'rish va qulaylik hissiyotini oshirish orqali salomatlikni ta'minlashda muhimdir. To'g'ri tanlangan optik qurilmalar

salomatlikni oshirishda yordam bera oladi, chunki to'g'ri ko'z ko'rishi, boshqa kasalliklarni oldini olish, ish qilish va hayot sifatini oshirishga yordam beradi. Optik qurilmalar to'g'ri tanlanishi bilan birga, o'zingizni ham qayd etish va ko'zingizdagi o'zgarishlarni kuzatib borishi muhimdir. Uzoq muddatli kompyuter ishlari, mobil qurilmalar, televizor va boshqa o'zgarishlar ko'zingiz uchun zahrarli o'zgarishlarga sabab bo'lishi mumkin. Optik qurilmalar, ularni bartaraf etish va ko'zingizni yaxshi ko'rish uchun muvofiq maslahatlar berishda yordam beradi. Optik qurilmalar, har bir insonning hayot sifatini va faollik darajasini oshirishda muhim bo'lishi mumkin. Yaxshi ko'rish, ma'lumotlarni o'qish, ish qilish va boshqa faoliyatlar uchun to'g'ri tanlangan optik qurilmalar salomatlikni ta'minlashda o'z hissasini qo'shadi. Optik qurilmalar, ko'zingizdagi nuqsonlarning oldini olishda yordam bera oladi. Misol uchun, miopiya yoki astigmatizmni to'g'rilash optik qurilmalar orqali amalga oshiriladi va bu xatoliklarni bartaraf etish salomatlikni oshirish uchun muhimdir. Optik qurilmalar yordamida salomatlikni oshirish uchun, kuzatib borish va tibbiy maslahatlar qabul qilish, oftalmolog bilan tanishib chiqish tajribasi eng muhimdir. Zamonaviy tibbiyotda, optik qurilmalar va ularning davriy yechimlari hayotni yanada qulay qilish uchun bir qancha muhim imkoniyatlar yaratadi. Quyidagi, zamonaviy tibbiyotdagi optik qurilmalarni integratsiyasi va ularning o'zgartirilgan ilovalarini bildiradi: Laserlar zamonaviy tibbiyotda ko'z xatoliklarini davolash uchun intensiv tarqalgan yoritma va optik qurilmalarni o'z ichiga olgan texnologiya. Lazer xirurgiya va PRK (Photorefractive Keratectomy) kabi lazerdan foydalanadigan optik xirurgiya usullari ko'zingizdagi miopiya, gipermetropiya, astigmatizm va presbiopiyani o'zgartirish uchun ishlatiladi. Zamonaviy tibbiyotda, ko'zni to'g'ri ko'rish uchun monitoring qilish texnologiyalari va qurilmalar o'z o'zini o'zgartirayotgan, takomillashtirayotgan holatda ko'zning ko'rish davrini kuzatib borish uchun ishlatiladi. Telemedicine tizimlari va smart tech qurilmalari, oftalmolog bilan maslahatlashish va monitoring qilishni osonlashtirish uchun ishlatiladi. Ko'zning xolatini tekshirish va maslahat berish, insonlarga yangi optik qurilmalarni tanlashda yordam beradi. Zamonaviy tibbiyotda, biomateriallar, ko'zning jismoniy jihatdan o'ziga xos xususiyatlarni o'z ichiga olgan optik qurilmalar yaratishda ishlatiladi. Bu, insonlarning optik qurilmalarni hissiy va qulayroq his qilishiga yordam beradi. Genetika va personalizatsiya asosida tibbiy tajribani individual tahlil qilish, insonning genetik xususiyatlariga ko'ra maxsus optik qurilmalar va davolash rejimlarini tuzish uchun muhim bo'lgan xususiyatlarni aniqlashda ishlatiladi. Zamonaviy tibbiyot va optika sohasidagi yangiliklar, insonlarni ko'z

xatoliklarini to'g'rilash va ko'zni qulay ko'rishda yangi yondashuvlarga olib kelmoqda. Bu yangiliklar insonlarning hayotini yanada qulayroq va faolroq qilishga imkon beradi. Optik qurilmalar, ko'zni to'g'rilashda o'rtacha foydalaniladigan vositalardir, lekin ular boshqa sohalarda ham qo'llanilishi mumkin. Optik qurilmalar, kompyuter ishlab chiqarish, dizayn, grafika va boshqa texnikaviy sohalarda ishlayotgan insonlar uchun foydalidir. Ko'zni o'rganishda ishlatiladigan kompyuter monitoriga qarash va uzoq muddatli kompyuter ishlari jarayonlarida miopiya, ghipermetropiya va astigmatizmni to'g'rilash uchun optik qurilmalar foydali bo'ladi. Optik qurilmalar, musiqa va san'at sohasida faol ishlayotgan insonlar uchun muhim bo'lishi mumkin. Optik qurilmalar, amaliyotlar, maishiy texnika ishlab chiqarish, tezkor ta'lim, ma'rifat olish va boshqa ko'plab sohalarda foydalash uchun ideal bo'lib turadi. Optik qurilmalar, o'zgaruvchilar, mikroskoplar, teleskoplar va boshqa optik asboblardan bilan birga ishlatilishi mumkin. Fotografiya, videography sohalari optik qurilmalardan foydalash uchun idealdir. Miopiya yoki astigmatizmni to'g'rilash orqali fotograflar va video materiallarni chizish va to'g'ri ko'rish imkoniyatini oshirish mumkin. Teleskoplar va boshqa astronomiyaviy vositalar optik qurilmalardan intensiv ravishda foydalanadi. Yulduzlar va sayyoralar sistemalarini ko'rish uchun optik qurilmalar katta ahamiyatga ega.

Xulosa.

Optik qurilmalar ko'p sohada foydalaniladi. Bu qurilmalar optika sohasida keng qamrovli amaliyotlarni bajarishda, tashqi va ichki ob'yektlarni ko'rish, ko'rsatish va boshqarishda foydalaniladi. Hozirgi kunda, optik qurilmalar bir nechta sohalarda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Optika tibbiyot sohasida yirik rol o'ynaydi. Mammografi, MRI (Magnet rezonans tomografiyasi), endoskopi, mikroskoplar va boshqa tibbiyotdagi texnologiyalarda foydalaniladigan optik qurilmalar, davolash va diagnoz qo'yishda, shuningdek, davolash jarayonlarini o'rganish uchun keng qamrovli rasm olishda muhimdir. Optik qurilmalar, ko'p sohada ko'p sonli ma'lumotni o'tkazib yuborishda, telekommunikatsiya sohasida ham muhimdir. Optik kabel tarmoqlari, internet va telefon xizmatlarini tez va qat'iy o'tkazish uchun keng qamrovli optik qurilmalardan foydalaniladi. Optik qurilmalar, kompyuter texnologiyalarining bir qancha komponentlarini o'z ichiga oladi. Masalan, optik disk haydash va o'qitish uchun foydalaniladi, shuningdek, lazer optik tizimlar kompyuter printerlarida ishlatiladi. Optik qurilmalar, fotosurat olamida keng qamrovli va yaxshi sifatli rasmlar olishda muhimdir. Kameralar, teleskoplar, mikroskoplar va boshqa optik qurilmalar fotosurat olish va nazorat qilish uchun foydalaniladi. Lazerlar, optik qurilmalar

yordamida yaratiladi va ularga optik boshqaruv tizimlari yordamida nazorat qilinadi. Lazerlar, ko'p sohalarda, masalan, ko'rsatkichlarda, tibbiyotda, kommunikatsiyada va boshqa texnologiyalarda foydalaniladi. Optik qurilmalar, xususan, nanotexnologiya, kibernetika, va boshqa sohalarda ham keng qamrovli amaliyotlarni bajarishda va ma'lumotlarni o'rgatishda foydalaniladi. Optik qurilmalar, ko'p sohalarda ishlatiladigan texnologik asboblardan bo'lib, muhim sifatga ega. Bu qurilmalar soha nomzodlari uchun keng imkoniyatlar yaratishda va texnologik rivojlanishda o'rin oladi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Bobokulova, M. (2024). IN MEDICINE FROM ECHOPHRAPHY USE. Development and innovations in science, 3(1), 94-103.
2. Bobokulova, M. (2024). INTERPRETATION OF QUANTUM THEORY AND ITS ROLE IN NATURE. Models and methods in modern science, 3(1), 94-109.
3. Bobokulova, M. (2024, January). RADIO WAVE SURGERY. In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 3, No. 1, pp. 56-66).
4. Bobokulova, M. (2024). UNCERTAINTY IN THE HEISENBERG UNCERTAINTY PRINCIPLE. Академические исследования в современной науке, 3(2), 80-96.
5. Bobokulova, M. (2024). BLOOD ROTATION OF THE SYSTEM PHYSICIST BASICS. Инновационные исследования в науке, 3(1), 64-74.
6. Bobokulova, M. (2024). THE ROLE OF NANOTECHNOLOGY IN MODERN PHYSICS. Development and innovations in science, 3(1), 145-153.
7. Bobokulova, M. X. (2023). STOMATOLOGIK MATERIALLARNING FIZIK-MEXANIK XOSSALARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(9), 223-228.
8. Xamroyevna, B. M. (2023). ORGANIZM TO 'QIMALARINING ZICHLIGINI ANIQLASH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 50-58.
9. Bobokulova, M. K. (2023). IMPORTANCE OF FIBER OPTIC DEVICES IN MEDICINE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 212-216.
10. Xhamroyevna, M. B. (2023). PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF BIOLOGICAL MEMBRANES, BIOPHYSICAL MECHANISMS OF MOVEMENT OF SUBSTANCES IN THE MEMBRANE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 217-221.
11. Bobokulova, M. K. (2024). TOLALI OPTIKA ASBOBLARINING TIBBIYOTDAGI AHAMIYATI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 517-524.
12. Latipova, S. (2024). YUQORI SINF GEOMETRIYA MAVZUSINI O'QITISHDA YANGI PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA METODLAR. SINKVEYN METODI,

- VENN DIAGRAMMASI METODLARI HAQIDA. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 3(3), 165-173.
13. Latipova, S. (2024, February). SAVOL-JAVOB METODI, BURCHAKLAR METODI, DEBAT (BAHS) METODLARI YORDAMIDA GEOMETRIYANI O'RGANISH. In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 3, No. 2, pp. 25-33).
14. Latipova, S., & Sharipova, M. (2024). KESIK PIRAMIDA MAVZUSIDA FOYDALANILADIGAN YANGI PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALAR. 6X6X6 METODI, BBB (BILARDIM, BILMOQCHIMAN, BILIB OLDIM) METODLARI HAQIDA. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 3(2), 40-48.
15. Latipova, S. (2024). 10-11 SINFLARDA STEREOOMETRIYA OQITISHNING ILMIY VA NAZARIY ASOSLARI. Академические исследования в современной науке, 3(6), 27-35.
16. Latipova, S. (2024). HILFER HOSILASI VA UNI HISOBLASH USULLARI. Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций, 3(2), 122-130.
17. Latipova, S. (2024). HILFER MA'NOSIDA KASR TARTIBLI TENGLAMALAR UCHUN KOSHI MASALASI. Development and innovations in science, 3(2), 58-70.
18. Latipova, S. (2024). KESIK PIRAMIDA TUSHUNCHASI. KESIK PIRAMIDANING YON SIRTINI TOPISH FORMULALARI. Models and methods in modern science, 3(2), 58-71.
19. Shahnoza, L. (2023, March). KASR TARTIBLI TENGLAMALARDA MANBA VA BOSHLANG'ICH FUNKSIYANI ANIQLASH BO'YICHA TESKARI MASALALAR. In "Conference on Universal Science Research 2023" (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 8-10).
20. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2024). CAPUTO MA'NOSIDAGI KASR TARTIBLI TENGLAMALARDA MANBA FUNKSIYANI ANIQLASH BO 'YICHA TO 'G 'RI MASALALAR. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 375-382.
21. Latipova, S. S. (2023). SOLVING THE INVERSE PROBLEM OF FINDING THE SOURCE FUNCTION IN FRACTIONAL ORDER EQUATIONS. Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal, 1(10), 13-23.
22. Latipova, S. (2024). GEOMETRIYADA EKSTREMAL MASALALAR. В DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN MODERN SCIENCES (T. 3, Выпуск 3, сс. 163–172).
23. Latipova, S. (2024). EKSTREMUMNING ZARURIY SHARTI. В SOLUTION OF SOCIAL PROBLEMS IN MANAGEMENT AND ECONOMY (T. 3, Выпуск 2, сс. 79–90).

24. Latipova, S. (2024). FUNKSIYANING KESMADAGI ENG KATTA VA ENG KICHIK QIYMATI. В CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES (Т. 3, Выпуск 2, сс. 120–129).
25. Latipova, S. (2024). EKSTREMUMLARNING YUQORI TARTIBLI HOSILA YORDAMIDA TEKSHIRILISHI. IKKINCHI TARTIBLI HOSILA YORDAMIDA EKSTREMUMGA TEKSHIRISH. В SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM (Т. 3, Выпуск 3, сс. 122–133).
26. Latipova, S. (2024). BIR NECHA O'ZGARUVCHILI FUNKSIYANING EKSTREMUMLARI. В THEORETICAL ASPECTS IN THE FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES (Т. 3, Выпуск 4, сс. 14–24).
27. Latipova, S. (2024). SHARTLI EKSTREMUM. В МЕЖДУРОДНАЯ КОНФЕРЕНЦИЯ АКАДЕМИЧЕСКИХ НАУК (Т. 3, Выпуск 2, сс. 61–70).
28. Latipova, S. (2024). KASR TARTIBLI HOSILALARGA BO'LGAN ILK QARASHLAR. В CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF EDUCATION AND INNOVATION (Т. 3, Выпуск 2, сс. 46–51).
29. Latipova, S. (2024). TURLI EKSTREMAL MASALALAR. BAZI QADIMIY EKSTREMAL MASALALAR. В CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF EDUCATION AND INNOVATION (Т. 3, Выпуск 2, сс. 52–57).
30. Latipova, S. (2024). FUNKSIYA GRAFIGINI YASASHDA EKSTREMUMNING QO'LLANILISHI. В CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF EDUCATION AND INNOVATION (Т. 3, Выпуск 2, сс. 58–65).
31. Latipova, S. (2024). BIRINCHI TARTIBLI HOSILA YORDAMIDA FUNKSIYANING EKSTREMUMGA TEKSHIRISH, FUNKSIYANING EKSTREMUMLARI. В CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF EDUCATION AND INNOVATION (Т. 3, Выпуск 2, сс. 66–72).
32. Boboqulova, M. (2024). FIZIKA O'QITISHNING INTERFAOL METODLARI. В CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF EDUCATION AND INNOVATION (Т. 3, Выпуск 2, сс. 73–82).
33. Murodov, O. (2024). INNOVATIVE INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES AND NEW METHODS AND TOOLS FOR THEIR APPLICATION IN TODAY'S EDUCATION. В CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF EDUCATION AND INNOVATION (Т. 3, Выпуск 2, сс. 83–92).
34. Murodov, O. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF AN AUTOMATED PARAMETER CONTROL SYSTEM ROOMS AND WORKSHOPS BASED ON CLOUD TECHNOLOGIES. Академические исследования в современной науке, 3(2), 16-27. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). Zamonaviy ta'limda axborot texnologiyalari va

ularni qo 'llash usul va vositalari. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(11), 481-486.

35. Муродов, О. Т. (2023). РАЗРАБОТКА АВТОМАТИЗИРОВАННОЙ СИСТЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ТЕМПЕРАТУРЫ И ВЛАЖНОСТИ В ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННЫХ КОМНАТ. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(26), 91-95.

36. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). INFORMATIKA DARSLARINI TASHKIL ETISHDA INNOVATSION USULLARDAN FOYDALANISH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(32), 194-201.

37. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). INFORMATIKA FANINI O 'QITISHDA YANGI INNOVATSION USULLARDAN FOYDALANISH METODIKASI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 130-139.

38. Turakulovich, M. O. (2023). DEVELOPMENT AND INSTALLATION OF AN AUTOMATIC TEMPERATURE CONTROL SYSTEM IN ROOMS. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).

39. MURODOV, O. T. (2023). INNOVATIVE INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES AND NEW METHODS AND TOOLS FOR THEIR APPLICATION IN TODAY'S EDUCATION. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).

40. Muradov, O. (2024, January). APPLICATION OF BASIC PRINCIPLES AND RULES OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES TO EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES. In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 3, No. 1, pp. 46-55).

41. Muradov, O. (2024). BASIC PRINCIPLES AND RULES OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. Models and methods in modern science, 3(1), 84-93.

42. Muradov, O. (2024). APPLIED TO THE CURRENT TRAINING PROCESS REQUIREMENTS. Инновационные исследования в науке, 3(1), 54-63.

43. Murodov, O. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF AN AUTOMATED PARAMETER CONTROL SYSTEM ROOMS AND WORKSHOPS BASED ON CLOUD TECHNOLOGIES. Академические исследования в современной науке, 3(2), 16-27.

44. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g, Q. li.(2023). Mobil ilovalar yaratish va ularni bajarish jarayoni. International journal of scientific researchers, 2(2).

45. Karimov, F. (2022). ANIQ INTEGRALNI TAQRIBIY HISOBLASH. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz), 14(14).

46. Quvvatov, B. (2024). GLOBAL IN VIRTUAL LEARNING MOBILE APP CREATION INFORMATION SYSTEMS AND TECHNOLOGIES. Science and innovation in the education system, 3(1), 95-104.

47. Quvvatov, B. (2024). SQL DATABASES AND BIG DATA ANALYTICS: NAVIGATING THE DATA MANAGEMENT LANDSCAPE. Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences, 3(1), 117-124.
48. Quvvatov, B. (2024). CONSTRUCTION OF SPECIAL MODELS THROUGH DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS AND PRACTICAL SOLUTIONS. Solution of social problems in management and economy, 3(1), 108-115.
49. Quvvatov, B. (2024). FINDING SOLUTIONS OF SPECIAL MODELS BY INTEGRATING INTEGRAL EQUATIONS AND MODELS. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 3(1), 122-130.
50. Quvvatov, B. (2024). WEB FRONT-END AND BACK-END TECHNOLOGIES IN PROGRAMMING. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 3(1), 208-215.
51. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g, Q. (2023). USE OF ARTIFICIAL NERVOUS SYSTEMS IN MODELING. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 269-273.
52. Behruz Ulugbek og, Q. (2023). TECHNOLOGY AND MEDICINE: A DYNAMIC PARTNERSHIP. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(11).
53. Quvvatov, B. (2024). DIFFERENTIAL TENGLAMALAR VA AMALIY ECHIMLAR ORQALI MAXSUS MODELLARNI QURISH. Menejment va iqtisodiyotda ijtimoiy muammolarni hal qilish , 3 (1), 108-115.
54. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g', Q. (2023). SUN'IY NERV TIZIMLARIDAN MODELLASHDA FOYDALANISH. Fan va texnologiyaning ko'p tarmoqli jurnali , 3 (5), 269-273.
55. Behruz Ulug'bek og', Q. (2023). TEXNOLOGIYA VA TIBBIYOT: DİNAMİK HAMKORLIK. Tadqiqot va ishlanmalar bo'yicha xalqaro multidisipliner jurnali , 10 (11).
56. Quvvatov, B. (2024). ALGEBRAIK ANIQLIGI YUQORI BOLGAN KVADRATUR FORMULALAR. GAUSS KVADRATUR FORMULALARI. Models and methods in modern science, 3(2), 114-125.
57. Quvvatov, B. (2024). ALGEBRAIK ANIQLIGI YUQORI BOLGAN KVADRATUR FORMULALAR. ORTOGONAL KOPHADLAR. Инновационные исследования в науке, 3(2), 47-59.
58. Quvvatov, B. (2024, February). ALGEBRAIK ANIQLIGI YUQORI BOLGAN KVADRATUR FORMULALAR. REKURSIV TRAPETSIYALAR QOIDASI. In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 3, No. 2, pp. 41-51).

59. Tursunov, B. J., & Allanazarov, G. O. (2019). Perspektivnye tehnologii proizvodstva po uluchsheniyu kachestva benzina. Theory and practice of contemporary science, 3(45), 305-308.
60. Турсунов, Б. Ж., & Алланазаров, Г. О. (2019). Перспективные технологии производства по улучшению качества бензина. Теория и практика современной науки, (3 (45)), 305-308.
61. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). Analysis of Concepts About the Effect of an Explosion in Solid Wednesday. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 296-304.
62. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). Methods of Control of Explosion Energy Distribution in Rocks. Intersections of Faith and Culture: American Journal of Religious and Cultural Studies (2993-2599), 1(10), 108-117.
63. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). WASTE-FREE TECHNOLOGY FOR ENRICHMENT OF PURIFIC COPPER-ZINC ORE. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 288-293.
64. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). ANALYSIS OF MODERN METHODS FOR OIL SLUDGE PROCESSING. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 280-287.
65. Jumaev, K., & Tursunov, B. (2022, December). Environmentally friendly technology for obtaining fuel briquettes from oil waste. In IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science (Vol. 1112, No. 1, p. 012005). IOP Publishing.
66. Sharipova, M., & Latipova, S. (2024). TAKRORIY GRUPPALASHLAR. Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences, 3(3), 134-142.
67. Sharipova, M. (2024). TAQQOSLAMA TUSHUNCHASI VA UNING XOSSALARI. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 3(2), 68-78.
68. Sharipova, M. (2024). IKKI O'ZGARUVCHILI TENGSIZLIKLAR SISTEMASINI TAQQOSLAMALAR USULI BILAN YECHISH. Development and innovations in science, 3(2), 97-105.
69. Sharipova, M. (2024). BIRINCHI DARAJALI TAQQOSLAMALARNI YECHISH USULLARI. Solution of social problems in management and economy, 3(2), 60-69.
70. Latipova, S., & Sharipova, M. (2024). KESIK PIRAMIDA MAVZUSIDA FOYDALANILADIGAN YANGI PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALAR. 6X6X6 METODI, BBB (BILARDIM, BILMOQCHIMAN, BILIB OLDIM) METODLARI HAQIDA. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 3(2), 40-48.

71. Sharipova, M. (2024). IN THE FORM OF AN UNBOUNDED PARALLELEPIPED IN THE FIELD NONLOCAL BORDERLINE CONDITIONAL LINEAR THE REVERSE IS THE CASE. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 3(1), 105-116.
72. Sharipova, M. (2024). FUNCTIONAL SPACES. IN SHORT REFLECTION PRINCIPLE. *Current approaches and new research in modern sciences*, 3(1), 131-142.
73. Sharipova, M. (2024). A IS CORRECT OF THE INTEGRAL TO THE ECONOMY APPLICATIONS. *Solution of social problems in management and economy*, 3(1), 116-125.
74. Sharipova, M. (2024). ASYMMETRY AND KURTOSIS COEFFICIENTS. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 3(1), 216-225.
75. Sharipova, M. (2024). TWO MULTIPLE OF THE INTEGRAL APPLICATIONS. *Инновационные исследования в науке*, 3(1), 135-140.
76. Sharipova, M. P. L. (2023). CAPUTA MA'NOSIDA KASR TARTIBLI HOSILALAR VA UNI HISOBLASH USULLARI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(9), 360-365.
77. Sharipova, M. P. (2023). MAXSUS SOHALARDA KARLEMAN MATRITSASI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(10), 137-141.
78. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). APPROXIMATION OF FUNCTIONS WITH COEFFICIENTS. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(9), 135-138.
79. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). Applications of the double integral to mechanical problems. *International journal of sciearchers*, 2(2), 101-103.
80. Sharipova, M. P. L. (2023). FINDING THE MAXIMUM AND MINIMUM VALUE OF A FUNCTION ON A SEGMENT. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(9), 245-248.
81. Sharipova, M. P. (2023). FUNKSIYALARNI KOEFFITSIENTLAR ORQALI FUNKSIYALARNI YAKINLASHTIRISH HAQIDA MA'LUMOTLAR. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(34), 102-110.
82. Sharipova, M. (2023, December). RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN STRAIGHT LINES AND PLANES IN SPACE. In *Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 2, No. 12, pp. 60-66)*.
83. Sharipova, M. (2023). FRACTIONAL DERIVATIVES. *Академические исследования в современной науке*, 2(27), 106-113.
84. Sharipova, M. (2023). CORRECT PLACED AND CORRECT NOT PLACED ISSUES. *Models and methods in modern science*, 2(13), 115-121.

85. Sharipova, M. (2023). HEAT SPREAD EQUATION. Инновационные исследования в науке, 2(12), 50-56.
86. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). HIGH MATH SCORE AND INTERVAL ASSESSMENT. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 420-424.
87. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). IN HIGHER MATHEMATICS, THE EXTREMUM OF A MULTIVARIABLE FUNCTION. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 425-429.
88. Sharipova, M. P. (2024). ISSIQLIK TARQALISH TENGLAMASI UCHUN KOSHI MASALASI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 525-532.
89. Axmedova, Z. (2024). KOMPYUTER TESTLARINING MAQSADLARI, MAZMUNI VA TUZILISHI. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 3(3), 211-222.
90. Axmedova, Z. (2024). NODAVLAT O'QUV MARKAZLARI TIZIMI PLATFORMASI UCHUN MOBIL ILOVA YARATISH. Академические исследования в современной науке, 3(6), 162-179.
91. Axmedova, Z. (2024). NODAVLAT O'QUV MARKAZLARI TIZIMI PLATFORMASI UCHUN MA'LUMOTLAR BAZASINI YARATISH. Science and innovation in the education system, 3(3), 83-93.
92. Akhmedova, Z. (2024). STRUCTURES OF SMALL DATABASE MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS. Solution of social problems in management and economy, 3(1), 97-107.
93. Akhmedova, Z. (2024). DATA BY COMBINING MAIL THROUGH TO SEND METHODS. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 3(1), 198-207.
94. Akhmedova, Z., & Rahmatova, N. (2024). LMS (LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM) LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM FEATURES. Science and innovation in the education system, 3(1), 85-94.
95. Akhmedova, Z. (2024). CREATION OF A DATABASE FOR THE SYSTEM PLATFORM OF NON-GOVERNMENT EDUCATIONAL CENTERS. Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences, 3(1), 106-116.
96. Akhmedova, Z. (2024). IPHONE OPERATIONAL IN THE SYSTEM MOBILE APPLICATIONS TO CREATE INTENDED PROGRAMMING ENVIRONMENTS. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 3(1), 111-121.
97. Axmedova, Z. I. (2024). LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IMKONIYATLARI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 509-516.

98. Axmedova, Z. I. (2023). MA'LUMOTLAR BAZASI BOSHQARISH TIZIMLARI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 40-49.
99. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). CREATION AND PLACEMENT OF INTERACTIVE ELEMENTS. Solution of social problems in management and economy, 2(13), 120-128.
100. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). Programming Environments for Creating Mobile Applications on the Android Operating System. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 305-309.
101. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS, ELECTRONIC EDUCATION: TASKS AND OPPORTUNITIES. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 2(21), 171-177.
102. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). SQL (STRUCTURED QUERY LANGUAGE) CAPABILITIES OF THE STATISTICAL DATABASE LANGUAGE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 274-280.
103. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). SQL (STRUCTURED QUERY LANGUAGE) STATISTICAL PACKAGES OF CAPABILITIES. Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development, 2(12), 781-787.
104. Zulxumor, A. (2022). IMPLEMENTATION OF INTERACTIVE COURSES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. ILMIY TADQIQOT VA INNOVATSIYA, 1(6), 128-132.
105. Axmedova, Z. (2023). MOODLE TIZIMI VA UNING IMKONIYATLARI. Development and innovations in science, 2(11), 29-35.
106. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). USING THE USEFUL ASPECTS OF THE MOODLE SYSTEM AND ITS POSSIBILITIES. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 201-205.
107. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). USING THE USEFUL ASPECTS OF THE MOODLE SYSTEM AND ITS POSSIBILITIES. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 201-205.
108. Axmedova, Z. I. (2023). LMS TIZIMIDA INTERAKTIV ELEMENTLARNI YARATISH TEXNOLOGIYASI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(11), 368-372.
109. qizi Sharopova, M. M. (2023). RSA VA EL-GAMAL OCHIQ KALITLI SHIFRLASH ALGORITMI ASOSIDA ELEKTRON RAQMLI IMZOLARI. RSA OCHIQ KALITLI SHIFRLASH ALGORITMI ASOSIDAGI ELEKTRON RAQAMLI IMZO. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(10), 316-319.

110. Sharopova, M. M. qizi . (2023). JAVA TILI YORDAMIDA OB'EKTGA YUNALTIRILGAN DASTURLASH ASOSLARI BILAN TANISHISH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 111-119.
111. Sharopova, M. (2023). CHOOSE: COMPOSITION OR INHERITANCE. Science and innovation in the education system, 2(13), 96-102.
112. Sharopova, M. (2023). JAVA PROGRAMMING IN THE LANGUAGE HERITAGE TO DO SYNTAX. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 2(12), 82-87.
113. Sharopova, M. (2023). ARRAY AND ARRAYS INSTALLATION. Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences, 2(12), 102-107.
114. Sharopova, M. (2023). CLASSES AGAIN APPLY. Solution of social problems in management and economy, 2(13), 106-111.
115. qizi Sharopova, M. M. (2023). INTRODUCING" PROGRAM CONTROL OPERATORS" IN THE JAVA PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 222-231.
116. qizi Sharopova, M. M. (2023). Working with folders in the JAVA programming language. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 232-236.
117. Sharopova, M. (2024). CREATION OF A DATABASE FOR THE SYSTEM PLATFORM OF NON-GOVERNMENT EDUCATIONAL CENTERS. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 3(1), 185-191.
118. Sharopova, M. (2024). DSA ERI STANDARD. ELECTRONIC DIGITAL SIGNATURE OF GOST R 34.10-94. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 3(1), 169-178.
119. Sharopova, M. (2024). COLLECTORS.(OBJECT CONTAINERS). Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences, 3(1), 93-101.
120. Sharopova, M. (2024). JAVA PROGRAMMING IN THE LANGUAGE FLOWING INPUT AND RELEASE. Solution of social problems in management and economy, 3(1), 84-93.